

EXAMINING THE FACTORS THAT CAN IMPROVE THE SUPERVISION OF STUDENTS IN PRISON

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ABSTRACT

The study examined factors that can improve the supervision of jailed students. The study was conducted at a penal institution situated in Namibia. This study utilized a qualitative research style, wherein data was gathered through recorded interviews. The sample consisted of 12 incarcerated students who engaged in remote e-learning. The data was given to a proficient transcriber for examination. The transcriber faithfully replicated the recorded data verbatim and subsequently presented the transcriptions to the author for evaluation. Various factors can significantly enhance educational performance and rehabilitation endeavors in prison, hence impacting the effectiveness of student supervision. A crucial factor is the existence of skilled supervisors who have a deep comprehension of the specific needs of incarcerated students and are skilled at delivering educational content within a correctional setting. Equally important is the execution of tailored educational programs that prioritize both academic and vocational skills, so increasing the likelihood of securing job upon release. Access to essential resources, like textbooks, technology, and appropriate learning environments, enhances the effectiveness of supervision. Furthermore, it is crucial to provide a productive and effective educational setting within the penal system. This can be achieved by promoting cooperation between correctional personnel and educational providers to establish a secure and nurturing learning atmosphere. Regular assessment and feedback mechanisms facilitate the identification of students' progress and areas in need of improvement, e.g., educational methods that must be flexible and responsive. Furthermore, it is crucial to address the psychological and emotional needs of incarcerated students to improve their supervision.

Keywords: Rehabilitation, educational programs, correctional staff, learning environment, incarcerated students.

1. INTRODUCTION

The purpose of this study was to examine the factors that can improve the supervision of imprisoned students, with a particular emphasis on a prison in Namibia. The aim was to identify the essential elements that contribute to effective educational methods in a correctional environment. The study sought to gain more insights and to offer recommendations to enhance the educational experiences and outcomes of incarcerated individuals by examining the unique challenges and opportunities in correctional settings. Also, the study hinged on the importance of education as a method of rehabilitation and aimed at providing a framework for improving the

supervision and support given to students who are studying in prison. The primary goal of prison education in Namibia is to promote the rehabilitation and reintegration of incarcerated individuals into society by providing them with opportunities for education. Historically, Namibia's correctional system, influenced by its colonial past, faced significant challenges in providing comprehensive education to prisoners. However, in recent years, there has been a purposeful and concentrated effort to completely revamp the prison education system. The Namibian Correctional Service (NCS) has introduced a variety of initiatives that cover basic reading and numeracy, vocational training, and secondary education. These programs are specifically tailored to provide offenders with the essential skills and knowledge needed to enhance their prospects of securing employment and reduce the possibility of recidivism upon release. In addition, partnerships have been established with neighboring educational institutions and non-governmental organizations (NGOs) to offer additional assistance for these initiatives. Despite considerable progress, there are still unresolved challenges in the realm of correctional education that require attention. The issues encompass scarcity of resources, overcrowding in facilities, and the need for enhanced training for correctional educators. The long-term success of prison education in Namibia is strongly dependent on continuous investment and policy support.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Factors that Can Improve the Supervision of Students in Prison

Supervising students in jail is a crucial component of the educational and rehabilitation initiatives in the criminal justice system. Various elements can help to the efficient monitoring of these students, ultimately enhancing their educational performance and facilitating their successful reintegration into society. The security measures and overall atmosphere in the correctional institution can have a substantial influence on student conduct and misbehavior. Research has indicated that jailed juveniles who are in facilities with stronger security measures are more likely to engage in academic misconduct and aggressive behavior [1]. This implies that the physical setting of a facility might influence the conduct of students and the difficulties they encounter in their educational pursuits. Prior experiences of students can also have an impact on their behavior and educational achievements while they are in prison. Studies have demonstrated that negative experiences throughout childhood, such as abuse, neglect, and dysfunctional households, can lead to higher levels of violence and academic misconduct among young individuals involved in the legal system [1]. It is essential to acknowledge the influence of Adverse Childhood Experiences (ACEs) and offer trauma-informed assistance to enhance the oversight and rehabilitation of these students.

The behavior and academic progress of jailed students might also be influenced by their social and emotional skills. Research has shown that adolescents who possess advanced emotional and communicative skills, indicating a greater degree of social competence, are less likely to engage in aggressive behavior and academic misbehavior while in prisons [1]. Improving the monitoring and rehabilitation of these students can be effectively achieved by enhancing their social and emotional learning. Delivering individualized assistance and implementing research-backed initiatives that are customized to the unique requirements of every imprisoned student can enhance the effectiveness of supervision. These interventions may encompass personalized educational plans, counseling, and specific measures to tackle behavioral difficulties, mental health issues, and

the enhancement of skills [2]. By catering to the individualized requirements of each student, the oversight and assistance can be more efficient in fostering favorable results.

The training and collaboration of professionals within the prison can also influence the oversight of jailed students. Providing comprehensive training to staff members on evidence-based methods, trauma-informed care, and effective behavior management approaches can improve their capacity to offer suitable supervision and assistance [2]. Moreover, the cooperation of specialists in the fields of education, corrections, and social services can enhance a more holistic approach to student supervision and rehabilitation. By considering these issues, correctional and educational institutions can collaborate to enhance the oversight of incarcerated students, effectively addressing their complex requirements and fostering their intellectual and social growth both while in jail and after their release. Efficient oversight of students in a prison is essential for promoting educational achievement and personal development among jailed inmates. Several things can contribute to improving the oversight of incarcerated students. This discourse will analyze pivotal elements and furnish pertinent illustrations. The proficiency and knowledge of the professionals overseeing the students is a crucial determinant. It is recommended that correctional officials and educational workers who work in prisons obtain specialized training in specific areas, including classroom management, conflict resolution, and trauma-informed techniques [3]. This guarantees that the staff possess the essential expertise to establish a secure and nurturing educational setting for the students. Another crucial consideration is the accessibility of resources and support services within the prison. Prisons must furnish sufficient educational resources, including current textbooks, advanced technology, and the opportunity to utilize online learning platforms [4]. Furthermore, the presence of counseling services, mental health support, and mentoring programs can significantly improve the general welfare and academic achievement of the students [5].

The participation and cooperation of diverse stakeholders, including prison authorities, educators, and community organizations, can help enhance the oversight of students in jail. By collaborating, these stakeholders may create and execute all-encompassing educational programs that effectively address the students' needs and provide customized supervision according to their individual requirements [6]. Moreover, the utilization of evidence-based methods and frequent program assessments can aid in identifying areas for enhancement and directing the creation of more efficient supervision procedures. For instance, the utilization of data-driven decision-making and the integration of student feedback can guide the improvement of supervision methods [7]. Hence, the supervision of students in a prison environment can be improved by aspects such as staff training and expertise, the provision of resources and support services, the cooperation of stakeholders, and the implementation of evidence-based practices and program evaluations. By attending to these characteristics, prisons can establish a conducive atmosphere that fosters scholastic achievement, individual development, and the effective reintegration of prisoners back into the community.

Supervising students in a jail environment poses distinct challenges that necessitate meticulous consideration of multiple issues. Several crucial variables that can enhance the monitoring of students in prison encompass: Teaching Methods and Approaches

The study, titled "Teaching Postgraduate Students in High Security Prison 2002-2011" by Josie Arnold, highlights the significance of acquiring knowledge about pedagogical techniques and approaches that are appropriate for teaching in a prison setting. According to [8], teaching in a high security jail is a mutually beneficial experience for both the teacher and the students, as it

provides a valuable learning opportunity. This implies that educators must modify their teaching methods and practices to cater to the unique requirements and difficulties encountered by jailed students. In the study conducted by [9], convicts, notably in New South Wales and Victoria, raised concerns about the attitudes of officers, lack of effective communication, and the overall environment in the prison system [9]. This emphasizes the crucial importance of effective communication and collaboration among jail personnel, educators, and students in creating a successful learning environment.

The study conducted by [9] highlights the importance of considering access and equity for jailed students, especially those who face extra obstacles such as language issues or deportation status. Meeting these needs is crucial for ensuring equal educational opportunities and promoting the academic achievement of incarcerated students.

According to Arnold [8], Beth O'Brien, an exceptional Education Leader from Kangan Batman TAFE, played a crucial role in enabling the jailed student to continue their schoolwork. This emphasizes the significance of cooperation between educational institutions and prison officials, as well as the necessity for institutional backing to facilitate and encourage educational possibilities for jailed individuals. The article by [10] highlights the importance of education in reducing recidivism rates among convicts. It emphasizes that education not only equips inmates with skills for work upon release but also enables them to successfully reintegrate into society, hence decreasing the likelihood of reoffending [10]. This implies that providing efficient oversight and assistance to incarcerated students can help diminish the probability of reoffending, which is a pivotal objective for the criminal justice system.

Overall, the analysis of the elements that can enhance student supervision in prison, as shown by the presented materials, underscores the necessity for a comprehensive and multifaceted strategy. This includes the examination of teaching methods, communication and coordination strategies, accessibility and fairness, collaboration, and the potential influence on the decrease of recidivism. By acknowledging and tackling these factors, educational institutions and prison authorities can collaborate to improve the educational possibilities and assistance provided to jailed students, eventually promoting their personal growth, and facilitating their successful reintegration into society.

2.2 Rationale

To examine the factors that can improve the supervision of students who are in prison. It is imperative to inform educational institutions and correctional services authorities about the significance of supplying incarcerated students with textbooks, digital tools, and internet resources to enhance their studying process. To cultivate a conducive educational atmosphere, it is imperative to furnish prisons with adequately equipped educational facilities, thereby affording inmates the vital resources to actively engage in their studies. The implementation of "individualized education plans" in educational institutions enables the tailoring of instruction to cater to the distinct needs of each inmate, considering their preferred learning styles and specific requirements. This personalized approach improves academic performance and addresses any barriers to learning.

2.3 Question

What factors can enhance the supervision of students in prison?

3. METHOD

3.1 Data collection

The study utilized a qualitative research technique, specifically focusing on obtaining detailed insights from student convicts identifying elements that could enhance their supervision. Information was gathered using tape-recorded interviews to ensure the acquisition of comprehensive and subtle responses. For this study, a deliberate selection was made of 12 student convicts who had specific experiences and viewpoints on the educational programs offered in the prison. The sampling approach specifically targeted persons who were enrolled in a distant education program, with a particular emphasis on those who were actively participating in educational activities while in prison. The interviews took place at a prison in Namibia, providing a distinctive contextual backdrop that impacts the conclusions of the study. This context facilitated the examination of the difficulties and advantages encountered by incarcerated students in this area. The inclusion of participants in a distant education program allowed for an in-depth examination of the efficacy and sufficiency of these programs, identifying specific areas where supervision and support might be enhanced. The collected qualitative data from these interviews was examined to find recurring patterns and elements that could improve the educational supervision of jailed students, hence aiding in their rehabilitation and successful reintegration into society.

3.2 Sampling Procedure

The study employed a purposive sample method to choose participants. To be more exact, a grand total of 12 students were chosen based on their involvement in a remote e-learning program while incarcerated. This methodology was used to ensure that individuals with direct experience of the educational programs offered in prisons were included, resulting in relevant and insightful data on the factors that can improve the supervision of students in these situations. The intentional selection facilitated a focused examination of persons who are actively engaged in educational pursuits, which is crucial for understanding the specific challenges and potential enhancements needed in their oversight.

3.3 Data analysis

To guarantee the precision and comprehensiveness of the obtained data, the interviews performed with the 12 incarcerated students were recorded using a tape-recorder. Later, these recorded tapes were given to a proficient transcriber who has a high level of expertise in the English language. The transcriber diligently listened to each tape-recorded interview and transcribed the conversations verbatim, assuring the accurate capture of every phrase and detail. Upon completion of the transcribing procedure, the author received the transcribed interviews for analysis. The author utilized an interpretive framework to examine the data, which involves understanding and attributing significance to the participants' experiences and viewpoints. This paradigm emphasises

the subjective importance of the participants' responses and seeks to examine the underlying themes and patterns in the data. The author performed a thorough examination of the transcriptions, carefully identifying important themes and insights related to the supervision of students in prison. The interpretive analysis involved coding the data, categorizing similar responses, and drawing connections between the statements made by different participants. This technique enabled the author to gain a deep understanding of the factors that can improve the supervision of incarcerated students, as perceived by the students themselves. The author employed a systematic and meticulous methodology to examine the data, ensuring that the conclusions were grounded in the actual experiences and perspectives of the incarcerated students. This analysis offered valuable perspectives on potential improvements in their educational oversight.

4. RESULTS/FINDINGS

The participants were asked the following question, namely: “State any factors that can improve the supervision of students in prison”.

Participant 1 said, “I think the tertiary institution they must give us more time”. and also, they are supposed to give us enough data to use so that we have got slow internet”.

Participant 2 said, “Luckily by means of our families we bought the Wi-Fi and then there is a government internet, but it is too slow that on my case sometimes like now I lost my two modules, I need to write it property because of the internet problem”.

Participant 3 said, “If the institution could assist us things like other institutions, they are being assisted with the data it will be very nice for me”.

Participant 4 said, “Factors that can improve the supervision of students in prison, is this one I think it now depends to the correctional services, especially officers”.

Participant 5 said, “Ja, because one thing they have to recruit or give more officers who work at the education department so that it will be flexible for supervision, especially because us here we need to be supervised when we are on the internet, we need the officers so you might find that there is one officer at a time, so this is not enough for the supervision to further your studies”.

Participant 6 said, “I think, I think it is the best, or I think one of the factors that can improve supervision is if the institutions understand like the circumstances in which we operate, or in which we study. If they better understand the challenges which we face and the difficulties which we have to, which we face on a daily basis, especially when it comes to non-understanding or when we have difficulty in understanding or disruption, concepts in our modules whereby the lecturer or whereby we have to get the platform through which we have to get assistance to be able to understand or better understand the modules”.

Participant 7 said, “The involvement of your lecturer or supervisor in assisting students to the student is paramount since we have some issues of communication and time, resources. The lecturers should go the extra mile in trying to assist the student whenever possible”.

Participant 8 said, “I think if they could allow students who are studying to have his own cell where he has a computer, where he has his study material, where he has access to light, 24 hours. Where

you will know there is no interference, if they can do that, all the prisoners, people who are interested in studying”.

Participant 9 said, “Good communication with your supervisors if the students are given proper communication, the time and equipment to communicate with the supervisor then at least improve the supervision whilst in prison”.

Participant 10 said, “Okay, as I said, the universities or institutions are providing services to us, they must at least give us for once per week classes, face to face classes because some of us, when we are teach that is the time that we can have something, you know when your own life, when you are online, you do not even have appetite to read. So, it will be better to give classes to inmates, also once per week, or during the weekends. What we will need from the institution is prompt response like if I have a task to do, or I am busy with my research, we should expect the supervisor to reply on time and the other thing is if we can get our assessments on time also because our time here is limited on the computer”

Participant 11 said, “So, the more time we are having, the better it will be. The institution also need to be involved also, the correctional officer must also be involved more especially the time for writing or maybe writing ... unclear ... who cannot be able to, from there at the beginning of the semester just to give them what they need, regardless what they should expect and how the system operate so that they be aware that once they produce one, what do they require and what should you do when approaching the questions, because I myself I would say you find it difficult you are moving from the level you are going to the tertiary level”.

Participant 12 said, “The factors which will improve to have more members assigned, because of a good example is if you get in the correctional facility one of the biggest facilities in Namibia, consist of 1000 plus offenders and having all these offenders it is for me, it is we are far away, I mean to achieve the goal of being a fellow prison because through education one can, it is a means of rehabilitation as the late Madiba have alluded to. It is the powerful to be a better person in future. Our constitution is very clear. The education policy that we have in prison says tertiary students in only 10%. My advice to NCS is to revise the policy and to make it accessible for all of us and then to the supervisor, to be more lenient and to get lecturers in to guide us so that this place where we are studying is too small, get us extra classes so that we are less than I think 45 students at the present moment, but if we encourage the others to come and study the place will be too small”.

5. DISCUSSION

The participants have articulated numerous significant issues pertaining to the difficulties they encounter in obtaining high-quality education and supervision during their incarceration. Participant 2 emphasized the need of higher schools allocating more time and enough data resources to students, since slow internet can be a substantial hindrance. This assertion is supported by a study on the influence of digital disparities on the educational encounters of jailed individuals [11].

Participant 3 proposed that colleges should help detained students with data, in a manner similar to how other institutions provide such support. This is consistent with the existing research that emphasizes the significance of offering sufficient resources and assistance to guarantee fair and equal access to education for jailed individuals [12].

Participant 4 highlighted the necessity for correctional services, specifically the officers, to assume a more proactive role in supervising students within the jail. Participant 5 concurred with this viewpoint, proposing that an increase in the recruitment of officers in the education department is necessary to ensure adequate supervision, particularly for online learning [13].

Participant 6 emphasized the significance of institutions gaining a deeper understanding of the distinct situations and difficulties encountered by jailed students. This understanding can then be used to develop more efficient techniques for providing support and supervision [14]. Participant 7 highlighted the significance of lecturer or supervisor engagement in aiding learners, a notion corroborated by research on the beneficial influence of robust student-faculty connections on academic achievements for jailed individuals [15].

Participant 8 suggested the concept of providing students with individualized compartments equipped with essential resources, such as computers and study materials, to reduce disruptions and enhance the learning environment. This suggestion is in line with the research that emphasizes the significance of establishing supportive and suitable learning settings for jailed students [16].

Participants 9 and 10 highlighted the necessity of enhancing communication and contact between students and their supervisors or institutions. This includes offering in-person classes and promptly addressing student inquiries. This aligns with studies that have shown the beneficial effects of effective communication and active involvement on the educational experiences of jailed individuals [12].

Participant 11 emphasized the significance of giving imprisoned students explicit expectations and advice on academic obligations. This can assist them in successfully transitioning to higher education [17]. Participant 12 proposed modifying the policy to enhance the accessibility of university education for jailed individuals. They also emphasized the necessity of more supervision and support from lecturers, as well as the provision of additional classroom spaces [14].

Overall, the participants' statements have emphasized various crucial elements that can enhance the oversight and assistance provided to incarcerated students. These elements include the allocation of sufficient resources and infrastructure, improved communication and involvement with institutions and supervisors, and a deeper comprehension of the distinct obstacles encountered by this demographic. These observations are consistent with the current body of research on successful educational strategies for jailed inmates.

6. IMPLICATIONS FOR PRACTICE AND POLICY

6.1 Implications for Practice: Personnel responsible for overseeing student detainees should undergo continuous training in educational approaches, trauma-informed care, and correctional education practices. This can improve their capacity to offer efficient assistance and direction. Sufficient educational resources, including textbooks, computers, and internet connection, are necessary for optimal learning outcomes. Classrooms should be designed to create an environment that is favorable to learning, equipped with suitable amenities and resources. Creating Individualized Education Programs (IEPs) for incarcerated students can effectively target their unique educational requirements and objectives. Supervisors should collaborate closely with educational personnel to customize these plans. Offering mental health assistance is essential, as numerous prisoners have undergone traumatic experiences and may suffer from mental health

conditions that affect their ability to study. Supervision should encompass the provision of counseling and psychological services. Involving relatives and communities in the educational process might offer supplementary assistance and encouragement for incarcerated students. Programs should incorporate strategies to engage families, such as organizing family visits and facilitating communication. Effective supervision must encompass, among other things, the preparation of student detainees for their reintegration into society. This entails providing vocational training, life skills programs, and assistance for pursuing further education after being released.

6.2 Implications for Policy: It is imperative for policies to require consistent professional development and allocate funds for training programs. This guarantees that the supervisory personnel are adequately prepared to address the distinct requirements of student detainees. Policies should guarantee the provision of adequate financial resources for educational resources and infrastructure within prisons. This encompasses the task of guaranteeing the availability of digital resources and contemporary instructional technologies. Mandatory policies should be implemented to ensure the creation of Individualized Education Programs (IEPs) for every incarcerated student. These IEPs should be subject to frequent evaluations and updates to monitor their advancement and make any required modifications. It is imperative for policies to require the inclusion of mental health services in educational programs in prisons, guaranteeing the presence of enough resources and qualified specialists. Policies should promote family and community involvement by granting flexible visitation privileges and communication channels, as well as endorsing activities that connect inmates with their support networks.

7. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, enhancing the oversight of incarcerated students is a complex task that necessitates a holistic strategy involving instruction, funding, personalized strategies, psychological assistance, involvement of families, programs for reintegration, evaluation, and cooperation. Providing continuous professional development to supervisory staff improves their capacity to offer effective support. Sufficient educational resources and infrastructure are essential for establishing an optimal learning environment. Customized Individualized Education Plans (IEPs) designed to meet the specific needs of each incarcerated individual can enhance educational outcomes, while the provision of mental health assistance tackles underlying factors that may impede the learning process. Family and community engagement are essential for offering emotional support and fostering motivation, which are vital in facilitating the rehabilitation process. Efficient reintegration programs that adequately equip prisoners for their lives after being released are crucial for decreasing repeat offenses and fostering favorable society reintegration. Consistent evaluation and responsibility guarantee the efficacy and ongoing enhancement of educational programs. Furthermore, partnering with external groups can provide supplementary resources and specialized knowledge, enhancing the educational opportunities for incarcerated students. Policy frameworks could ensure the success of these programs by requiring training, allocating funding, and promoting partnerships. Implementing a comprehensive strategy that caters to the various requirements of student inmates not only enhances their educational encounters but also enhances their general welfare and facilitates their successful reintegration into society. By considering and acting on these variables, we may establish a prison education system that enables convicts, diminishes the likelihood of reoffending, and promotes a just and impartial society.

8. RECOMMENDATIONS

Higher education institutions should provide frequent and thorough training programs for supervisory personnel that specifically concentrate on instructional methodologies, trauma-informed care, and correctional education practices. There have to be highly skilled personnel who are more prepared to address the distinct requirements of student convicts, cultivating a supportive and efficient educational setting. Prisons must be outfitted with essential educational resources, including textbooks, digital tools, and internet connection, to assure their availability. Personalized education strategies should be implemented to accommodate individual characteristics and optimize educational outcomes for each incarcerated student. Furthermore, it is imperative to incorporate mental health services into educational programs to ensure that jail students have access to counseling and psychological assistance.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The author expresses gratitude to the National Research Council of Namibia and the Correctional Authorities of Namibia, and the University of South Africa's Research Ethics Committee. Permissions were granted from both the author's institution [Ethical Clearance Certificate Ref: 2022/11/09/90284259/04/AM] and from the Namibian authorities for the research to be carried out.

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